

Computing & Allied Engineering Domain in India with reference to Private Universities: A Case Study of Bachelors Programs

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Abstract

Computing has been considered as important tools and technologies for information activities ranging from collection, selection, organization, processing, management, and dissemination of information. Computer Science including other allied fields becomes important for the creation of computation systems around the world. As the progress in the computing technology continues in the society, many universities around the world have started Computing and Information Technology related degrees. India is rising rapidly in terms of many things including economy and education. As a developing country, India is shining and growing rapidly in the education sector through its liberal higher education policies. India is considered as one of the important nations for the growth in Engineering education and skill development. India holds world largest higher educational institutions and about eight hundreds of them are degree awarding bodies. There are good numbers of Engineering programs mainly offered in the Engineering and Technological Colleges and Universities of different kinds. In recent past among the Higher educational Institutes in India Engineering programs have been started rapidly in private universities. This study provides a detailed overview of higher educational institutions in India emphasizing Engineering sectors. This study provides a strong focus on computing and information technology related programs available in private universities in India in Engineering segment.

Keywords :

Information, Information Technology, Computing, Higher Educational Institutions, HEIs, Engineering Degrees, Research, India, Developing Country.

Introduction :

India is tenth largest economy in the world as far as the present GDP is concerned. It is also third largest in purchasing power. Many activities were undertaken by the government for the growth and today India is one of the largest as well as the fastest growing economy in the world. Education is a driving force for the development and Engineering education play a crucial role in the development of India in different segments. India is well performing in engineering education and training segment for the promotion of skilled manpower in diverse areas [1], [5]. The infrastructure and quality of engineering education though questioned from various

industrial sectors in recent past but still India has many advantages and strengths in terms of Engineering and Technical education. The engineering education policy making council called AICTE is responsible for the designing, development, and administration of the engineering education in the Nation. AICTE also govern pharmacy, management, town and country planning, applied arts and crafts, hotel management and catering technology education. Though the engineering education, management, and computer application education may be freely governed by the universities of any kind approved by the UGC (The apex educational body in India), this has been started as per the order of Supreme Court. As a result, many universities in India have started technical and engineering education without the prior approval of AICTE. Many private universities have started Engineering programs leading to BTech (Bachelor of Technology), MTech (Master of Technology), BE (Bachelor of Engineering), ME (Master of Engineering) etc. Computing though most of the world mainly comes as Science field but in India, it is available both as Engineering and Sciences. Hence Computing related programs have been started with the Technology/Engineering stream mentioned above and also Bachelor/Masters of Science (abbreviated as BSc/BS, MSc/MS) programs [2], [7].

Objective

This is a conceptual paper based on the study of engineering education in India. The paper deals with the following aim and objectives—

- To learn about the Higher educational intuitions in India especially universities, colleges, and engineering institutions.
- To know about the engineering systems in India specially engineering education in the Engineering colleges.
- To learn about the related areas of Computing & Information Sciences as far as Engineering is concerned.
- To know the details of Engineering programs related to the computing and informatics available in the private universities in India.
- To learn about the engineering program's state wise availability and also its diversity at a glance.
- To dig out the latest skill-based programs in computing and also domain-based information science/ informatics programs.
- To learn about the manpower development strategies in engineering sectors as far as private universities are concerned.

Methodology Adopted

As it is a conceptual and theoretical framework so that some of the methodologies adopted to do the research work. Initially, literature review plays a great role in the development of the work especially for framing hypothesis and similar affairs. Gradually the web review played a vital

role to learn about the engineering systems and higher educational systems in India. The URL of AICTE, UGC studied carefully to reach the objectives. The private universities of the country are selected to learn about the status of engineering programs as far as computing and allied streams are concerned as per hypothesis. Private universities for sample collection are initially selected from UGC website approval list and gradually the website of every private university are studied to learn about the Computing degrees availability. The study conducted between August to October 2017. Hence the outcome of the computing engineering programs included the list of the offering of the university for the year 2017. Google results on News also considered as a methodology with the search quote on 'Engineering Education in India' to analyse the current strategies and situations of the computing engineering in India.

India, Higher Education and Engineering: An Overview

Engineering is a field of applied sciences there are many elementary inventions counting the wedge, lever, wheel, pulley etc. as far as Engineering education is concerned. It is now a day a common and important domain in training etc. According to the ABET “*The creative application of scientific principles to design or develop structures, machines, apparatus, or manufacturing processes, or works utilizing them singly or in combination; or to construct or operate the same with full cognizance of their design; or to forecast their behavior under specific operating conditions; all as respects an intended function, economics of operation or safety to life and property*” (Source: Wikipedia).

Table:1 - Showing Indian Universities at a glance

Universities	In Numbers
Central Universities	47
State Universities	370
State Private Universities	290
Deemed Universities	123
Total	823

India is seventh largest country and second most populated country (1.2 billion) in the world. It is also a place for ancient Indus valley civilization. Irrespective of many constraints and challenges faced by the country before and after independence due to the issues of *Poverty, Corruption, and Dishonesty, Inadequate public healthcare systems, Financial Constraint* etc., India is now set to provide quality higher education to many of its aspirant youngsters [3], [4]. Consequently, India is now a home for more than 40,000 colleges in professional and technical

areas offering Bachelors to Doctoral Programs in higher education. Though, universities are the highest level of educational institutions in the country established by the State Legislative Assembly or Parliament or UGC, there are about 90+ Institutions of National Importance (INI), which are super specialty institutions in diverse field such as Engineering, Management, Basic & Applied Science, Architecture, Pharmaceutical Sciences, Medical Sciences etc. These institutions are treated as important and greater value among the students as well as common people than even central universities due to the reason for their autonomy and financial status to make innovations and better quality education. Many of such institutions are also established and run by the Govt. of India viz. Bose Institute, Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics etc. (about 200+). A basic overview of Indian universities under four categories including Central Universities (5.7%), State universities (44.3%), Private universities (35%), and Deemed to be universities (15%) is depicted in Table: 1. Table 1 shows that presently India has a fair balance of government-owned universities (Central and State-owned together 50%) and private-owned universities (Private and Deemed together 50%).

AICTE is normally responsible for the areas of undergraduate engineering, postgraduate engineering, architecture, and management etc. It is important to note that the Doctoral Degrees will not fall under the jurisdiction of AICTE. *MTech (By Research)* as a research-based program in the field of Technological Sciences with a facility to recognize the internal or external research started by many universities worldwide. India holds a record number of technical institutes (around 10,000) under AICTE and with huge intake [5], [8]. As far as study considered by the year 2015-16 of AICTE India holds an intake of around 40,00,000 including all the technical studies falls under AICTE. However, as far as Engineering degrees are concerned (Bachelors level) it is around 17 Lakh whereas in MTech/ME level it is 8 Lakh. A detailed report provided by AICTE handbook is shown in Table 2.

Table: 2 Approved Institutions with Intake for 2015-16 (Source AICTE Handbook)

Region	State	Approved Programmes			Approved Intake			Total Approved Institutions	Total Approved Intake
		Diploma	PG	UG	Diploma	PG	UG		
Central	Chhattisgarh	68	45	62	11502	4776	23706	118	39984
	Gujarat	145	245	203	72670	32745	76704	429	182119
	Madhya Pradesh	179	369	306	36676	47465	110446	538	194587
Central Total		392	659	571	120848	84986	210856	1085	416690
Eastern	Andaman and Nicobar Islands	1	0	1	270	0	90	1	360
	Arunachal Pradesh	2	0	0	440	0	0	2	440
	Assam	13	21	21	2215	1992	5475	43	9682
	Jharkhand	33	14	18	9160	3089	7545	57	19794
	Manipur	1	1	1	100	40	115	2	255
	Meghalaya	3	2	1	380	150	480	6	1010
	Mizoram	2	2	1	180	62	30	3	272
	Nagaland	2	1	1	120	60	240	4	420
	Odisha	150	142	115	47015	17011	48959	304	112985
Sikkim	2	2	2	405	249	906	4	1560	

	Tripura	5	3	3	850	180	630	11	1660
	West Bengal	132	112	106	34962	13422	41038	256	89422
Eastern Total		346	300	270	96097	36255	105508	693	237860
North-West	Chandigarh	5	9	6	1025	1025	1546	13	3596
	Delhi	21	53	25	5865	13403	10080	82	29348
	Haryana	230	238	190	72488	30196	70394	452	173078
	Himachal Pradesh	39	33	37	10858	3078	10660	78	24596
	Jammu and Kashmir	32	18	9	6395	1696	3405	52	11496
	Punjab	190	190	148	67767	21954	50980	379	140701
	Rajasthan	251	166	172	63815	17055	65993	447	146863
North-West Total		768	707	587	228213	88407	213058	1503	529678
Northern	Bihar	47	37	28	14090	3067	9080	96	26237
	Uttar Pradesh	461	668	423	135942	95239	163616	1088	394797
	Uttarakhand	93	75	53	19233	7983	14754	161	41970
Northern Total		601	780	504	169265	106289	187450	1345	463004
South-Central	Andhra Pradesh	332	645	456	88696	102587	194460	855	385743
	Telangana	247	676	447	61980	128457	180583	791	371020
South-Central Total		579	1321	903	150676	231044	375043	1646	756763
South-West	Karnataka	359	368	268	101849	49411	109434	749	260694
	Kerala	73	223	208	22020	23064	65963	364	111047
South-West Total		432	591	476	123869	72475	175397	1113	371741
Southern	Puducherry	9	17	20	2830	1942	9030	31	13802
	Tamil Nadu	508	726	574	215043	85471	288717	1347	589231
Southern Total		517	743	594	217873	87413	297747	1378	603033
Western	Dadra and Nagar Haveli	1	2	1	330	186	60	3	576
	Daman and Diu	2	0	0	540	0	0	2	540
	Goa	9	5	8	2955	588	1430	17	4973
	Maharashtra	707	742	558	192998	95686	178472	1542	467156
Western Total		719	749	567	196823	96460	179962	1564	473245
Grand Total		4354	5850	4472	1303664	803329	1745021	10327	3852014

As far as universities are concerned India is a home to 279 private universities established in 29 states. The universities may be established by the act passed by the state legislative assembly hence the private universities are not established in union territories. The highest number of private universities established in Rajasthan (46) then Gujarat (30) followed by Uttar Pradesh (29). It is interesting to note that in some of the universities private universities not yet established such as Andhra Pradesh, Tamilnadu, Kerala, Jammu & Kashmir etc.

As far as the numbers of private universities offering engineering programs are concerned, Rajasthan stands first with 33 Engineering institutions offering BTech course. The Top ranking five states in terms of private universities offering BTech in Computing/ related fields include Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Gujarat, and Haryana as depicted in Table 3.

Table: 3 Top five States and no. of private universities offering B.Tech program in Computing

Serial No.	State	Private Universities with Engg. Programs
1	Rajasthan	33
2	Uttar Pradesh	26

3	Madhya Pradesh	20
4	Gujarat	16
5	Haryana/ HP	14

As far as the North Eastern States are concerned, Tripura is a home to only one private university where engineering (BTech) program already started. There are three private universities presently functioning in Nagaland but still, no one is started BTech program in Engineering.

Computing and Allied Technology Offering Universities in India: A State-wise Study

Universities in private sector are rising rapidly. Apart from the developed states, private universities have been established in different states of the nations with disadvantages such as Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Manipur, Bihar etc. Among the developed and big states, Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Karnataka etc. are also home to some of the finest private universities [6], [9]. Most the private universities located in the northern part of India. Rajasthan holds the highest number of private universities i.e. 46 and 33 of these universities offer BTech program in the areas of computing and information technology. Some of the Degrees offered in Bachelors level as far as Engineering course is concerned, Bachelor of Technology (BTech), and Bachelor of Engineering (BE) are mostly used. The number of universities offering at least one BTech in the areas of Computing/IT is identified and details are provided in Table 4. Here only UGC listed private universities (may be accessed at: <https://www.ugc.ac.in/privatuniversity.aspx>) are considered & analyzed.

Table: 4 Universities offering BTech in Computing: Case of Private Universities

Serial No.	States	No. of Universities	Universities with Engg. Unit (BTech)
1	Arunachal Pradesh	7	3
2	Assam	5	3
3	Bihar	2	1
4	Chhattisgarh	9	6
5	Gujarat	30	16
6	Haryana	20	14
7	Himachal Pradesh	17	14
8	Jharkhand	7	2
9	Karnataka	14	10
10	Meghalaya	8	1
11	Mizoram	1	1
12	Madhya Pradesh	24	20
13	Maharashtra	9	3
14	Manipur	1	0
15	Nagaland	3	0
16	Odisha	4	2
17	Punjab	15	10
18	Rajasthan	46	33

19	Sikkim	5	1
20	Tripura	1	1
21	Uttar Pradesh	29	26
22	Uttarakhand	13	6
23	West Bengal	9	8
Grand Total		279	180

It is important to note that many of the private universities even though have autonomy, are stick to the common and popular variations in BTech programs of computer science which include—

- Computer Science
- Computer Science and Engineering
- Information Technology
- Information and Communication Technology

However, few universities offer specializations based on emerging trends in information technology and industry. The details are depicted and discussed in next section.

Analysis of Computing & IT Educations in Engineering Track

Engineering is considered as an important and popular education domain as far as India is concerned. Traditionally, among the Engineering fields most popular were Civil Engineering, Electrical Engineering, Mechanical Engineering and later on apart from these core areas many new areas have emerged viz. Environmental Engineering, Bio-Technology, Computer Engineering, Information Technology etc.

Table: 5 Number of Universities offered BTech in IT and CSE both

Serial No.	States	No. of Universities	Universities with BTech-IT + BTech-CSE
1	Arunachal Pradesh	7	3
2	Assam	5	2
3	Bihar	2	Absent
4	Chhattisgarh	9	3
5	Gujarat	30	11
6	Haryana	20	6
7	Himachal Pradesh	17	2
8	Jharkhand	7	1
9	Karnataka	14	2
10	Meghalaya	8	1
11	Mizoram	1	Absent
12	Madhya Pradesh	24	10
13	Maharashtra	9	Absent
14	Manipur	1	Absent
15	Nagaland	3	Absent
16	Odisha	4	Absent

17	Punjab	15	2
18	Rajasthan	46	9
19	Sikkim	5	1
20	Tripura	1	Absent
21	Uttar Pradesh	29	9
22	Uttarakhand	13	2
23	West Bengal	9	Absent
Grand Total		279	63

In recent past the field of Computing and Information Technology became very much popular and apart from Computer Science and Engineering, Information Technology few other subjects also become popularized in India. As far as private universities are concerned few are offering skilled, enhanced and interdisciplinary subfields as well. Universities of the state of Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat offers BTech programs not only in popular Computer Science/CSE but also in Information Technology. According to this study 63 universities offering CSE and another related domain (viz. IT) as BTech, the details are depicted in Table: 5. However few other private universities from the states viz. Maharashtra, West Bengal, Odisha are only offering CS/CSE [8], [10].

Skill-based Engineering Programs: India into new height

Skills are very much important and valuable for the betterment of organizations, institutions, and individuals. Skills are important criteria for the work performance and employment. Universities and Higher Educational Institutions are moving towards introducing emerging programs and studies. Many universities in India as well are moving towards newer, emerging and skill-based domain and fields. Among the universities and HEIs private and deemed universities are doing well. Though State and Central Universities are working to consider such events but still not able to reach that height due to several issues [11], [12]. As far as emerging areas of Computing and Information Technologies are concerned few important domains include—

- Cloud Computing
- Big Data
- Mobile Based Applications
- Information and Cyber Security

Most of these areas treated as Information Technology field internationally, though CSE is treated as a combination of core computing, mathematical and theoretical foundations. The Table 6 shows that there is an increased interest among the private universities in offering emerging programs.

Table: 6 Number of Universities (state wise) offering skill based programs

Skill Based Specializations		
States	No. of Programs	No. of Private Universities

Assam	4	1
Gujarat	3	1
Haryana	16	8
Himachal Pradesh	6	4
Karnataka	1	1
Madhya Pradesh	9	2
Maharashtra	10	3
Odisha	2	1
Punjab	13	3
Rajasthan	14	5
Uttar Pradesh	28	5
Uttarakhand	25	3

It is interesting to note that many of such emerging areas and innovative subjects are offered in Computer Science and Engineering departments and even in BTech & MTech programs. As far as this study is concerned the highest numbers of institutions offering such programs are from Haryana and few other states viz. Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh etc. Some of the sample programs are—

- BTech-CSE (Banking & Finance)
- BTech-CSE (Business Analytics)
- BTech-CSE (Cloud Computing & Virtualization)
- BTech-CSE (Cyber Security)
- BTech-CSE (E-Commerce & Retail)

Table: 7- State-wise list (numbers) of Emerging program offering institutions

Serial No.	States	No. of Universities	Skill based Emerging Institutions
1	Arunachal Pradesh	7	Absent
2	Assam	5	1
3	Bihar	2	Absent
4	Chhattisgarh	9	Absent
5	Gujarat	30	2
6	Haryana	20	7
7	Himachal Pradesh	17	4
8	Jharkhand	7	Absent
9	Karnataka	14	Absent
10	Meghalaya	8	1
11	Mizoram	1	Absent
12	Madhya Pradesh	24	2
13	Maharashtra	9	5
14	Manipur	1	Absent
15	Nagaland	3	Absent

16	Odisha	4	1
17	Punjab	15	3
18	Rajasthan	46	3
19	Sikkim	5	Absent
20	Tripura	1	Absent
21	Uttar Pradesh	29	7
22	Uttarakhand	13	3
23	West Bengal	9	1
Grand Total		279	40

Though many universities have also started different types of programs, which deals with applications of IT and Computing in different areas viz. BTech-CSE (Banking & Finance)/ BTech-CSE (IoT & Smart Cities)/ BTech-CSE (Health Informatics) etc. However, it is important to note that among the universities and institutions most emerging skill-based programs may be treated as Cloud Computing, Big Data. *Fig 1* reports such skill-based programs at a glance. Here, the programs are classified into Cloud Computing, Cloud Allied Areas, Big Data, and Analytics.

Fig: 1-Showing number of emerging programs in the areas of IT with tag BTech-CSE

Cloud Computing scored and ranked first (about 27 private universities) whereas Big Data and Analytics scored as the second (about 26 private universities). It is important to note that some of the allied areas such as Cyber Security, IT Infrastructure Management, Networking etc. projected as a Cloud Allied programs and a large number of private universities offering the programs (total 21 in numbers). It is worthy to note that many universities have started BTech-CSE/IT

traditional format and BTech CSE with emerging areas. However, few universities are only offering specialized and emerging BTech-CSE programs viz. Galgalitas University, Neotia University, SRM University Haryana. Detailed program-wise private universities are listed in Table: 8.

Table: 8- Universities offering only skill based industry oriented BTech in IT & CSE areas

Serial No.	Universities	Programs
1	The Assam Royal Global University	BTech-CSE (Intelligent Computing/ Networking & Web Engineering/ Data Analytics & Engineering/ Software & Web Engineering)
2	Apeejay Stya University	BTech-CSE (Cloud Computing)
3	Jagan Nath University	BTech-CSE (Cloud Computing & Virtualization)-IBM BTech-CSE (Business Analytics)
4	SRM University, Haryana	BTech-CSE (Cloud & Mobile based Applications)-IBM BTech-CSE (Big Data & Analytics)-IBM BTech-Bio Informatics
5	Avantika University	BTech-CSE (Networking/ Security/ IoT/Computer Graphics/Cloud Computing/ Data Analytics/ AI/ Software Engineering)
6	MIT Art Design & Technology University	BTech-CSE (Intelligent Systems/Systems Engineering/ Network & Security) BTech-IT (Data Analytics)
7	Rayat Bahra University	BTech (CSE)-Android Development (Google)/ IoT & Java (Oracle)/ Database & Analytics (Oracle)/ Cyber Security & Forensic (IBM)/ IT Infrastructure Management (IBM)
8	University of Petroleum and Energy Studies	BTech-CSE (Digital Transformation Technologies)
9	Galgalitas University	BTech-CSE (Banking & Finance/ Business Analytics/ Cloud Computing & Virtualization/ Cyber Security/ E Commerce & Retail/ Graphics & Gaming/ Informatics/ IoT & Smart Cities/ IT Infrastructure/ Mainframe Technology/ Manufacturing Technology/ Mobile Computing/ Oil & Gas Informatics/ Telecom Informatics/ Health Informatics (all

		with IBM) BTech-CSE (Big Data/Dev. Ops- all with Xebia)
10	The Neotia University	BTech-CSE (Cyber Security)/(Data Analytics)-IBM

This trend now not only common in private universities but also deemed universities and some of the autonomous institutions. Though there are about 4,000 engineering colleges in the country it is difficult to introduce such industry oriented programs due to many constraints and challenges.

Beyond Traditional Characteristics and Programs on CSE

In Computing and Information Technological Sciences most common program is BTech-CSE as far as Indian engineering colleges are concerned. In case of the private universities also the challenging scenario is same. Although the next popular subject in this category is Information Technology, it is important to note that few universities are also offered Information and Communication Technology (ICT) programs, which is a combination of information technology and communication technology or rather IT with a focus on Communication Technology. Some universities importantly offer all the programs viz. CSE, IT and ICT. Table: 9 is showing the details of universities and programs.

Table: 9- Universities offering highest number of BTech in IT & Computing area

Serial No.	Higher Number of BTech (other than skill based)	
	Universities	Programs
1	Marwadi University, Rajkot	BE (ICT) BE (IT) BE (CSE)
2	Parul University, Vadodara	BTech (ICT) BTech (IT) BTech (CSE)
3	Manipal University, Jaipur	BTech (IT) BTech (CSE) BTech (Computer & Communication Engineering)

As per our study, the Information and Communication Technology program is become important and gradually started in many universities such as Parul University, PDP University, Ganpat University, Manipal University. Table: 10 is showing the details herewith.

Table: 10- Universities offering BTech-ICT instead of IT or with all the allied programs

Sl. No.	BTech in ICT or Allied Areas
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	Universities	Programs
1	Ahmadabad University	BTech-ICT
2	Ganpat University	BTech-ICT
3	Marwadi University	BTech-ICT
4	Pandit Deendayal Petroleum University	BTech-ICT
5	Parul University	BTech-ICT
6	Shri Vaishnav Vidyapeeth Vishwavidyalaya	BTech (Computer & Communication Engineering)
7	Chandigarh University	BE -Computer & Communication Engineering
8	Manipal University	BTech (Computer & Communication Engineering)

Merging domain raised popularity in recent past due to its need and promotion of the interdisciplinary research. In related field Information Science and Technology, Information Systems and Technology, Information Management and Technology, Computer and Information Sciences, Computer and Information Technology are popular worldwide. These subjects around the world mainly offered as BS program where as in India, it is offered as BTech/BE is offered. Hence, it is interesting to note that among the private universities only two are offering merged domain based Computing & IT degrees. Though it is important to note that instead of traditional domains of Computer and Information Sciences, Computer and Information Technology etc. the merged domain program offered as Computer Science & Information Technology. Such programs and universities are listed in Table 11.

Table: 11- Universities offering BTech-ICT instead of IT or with all the allied programs

Serial No.	BTech with combination of IT +CS	
	Universities	Programs
1	Symbiosis University of Applied Sciences, MP	BTech-CS & IT
2	PDM University, HR	BTech-CS & IT

Informatics (*which is responsible for the designing, development of information activities with technologies but with the solid concentration of information systems*) is a well established and popular domain in the field of Information Science and Computing. Many universities have started programs in the field of Informatics worldwide with BS or MS degrees. Even in many cases, it is treated as an alternative to IT or CS. In India, Informatics as a biased free (without any concentration) domain is available very limited only in the University of Delhi an MSc-Informatics is offered. Though worldwide Informatics is widely used in different sectors as well but in India, the term is restricted in nature. Only National Informatics Centre (NIC) is widely used various informatics.

Domain-based Informatics/ Information Science is very much popular in recent passed in international context. The advent of research and interdisciplinary affairs led various informatics branches and among them few informatics are—

- Bio Informatics
- Geo Informatics
- Business Informatics
- Health Informatics
- Eco Informatics
- Dental Informatics

It is worthy to note that among these domain-specific informatics the most practiced one is Bio Informatics. It is available at MSc/BTech/MTech levels in different type of universities. And the Geo Informatics program is also available in some of the universities. Hence the number of programs is higher than general Informatics. As far as private universities are concerned it worthy to note that a wide number of Informatics programs are offered (general & domain-specific) as BTech program. Importantly few are also general viz. Galgotias University, University of Petroleum and Energy Studies as an area of specialization (Table 12). Though, Bio Informatics program is offered as a full-fledged manner with BTech. Among the domain-based informatics first of its kind are (as far as BTech level is concerned)—

- Health Informatics
- Geo Informatics
- Tele Informatics etc.

Table: 12- Universities offering BTech with Informatics domains

Sl. No.	Informatics at BTech levels		
	Universities	Full-fledged	Specialization
1	Amity University, Gurgaon	BTech (Bio Informatics)	NA
2	SRM University, NCR	BTech-(Bio Informatics)	NA
3	Jaypee University of Information Technology, HR	BTech-(Bio Informatics)	NA
4	Galgotias University, UP	NA	BTech (H)-CSE (Informatics)
5	University of Petroleum and Energy Studies, UK	NA	BTech (H)-CSE (Informatics)
6	University of Petroleum and	NA	BTech (H)-CSE (Health Informatics)

	Energy Studies, UK		
7	University of Petroleum and Energy Studies, UK	NA	BTech (H)-CSE (Geo Informatics)
8	University of Petroleum and Energy Studies, UK	NA	BTech (H)-CSE (Tele Informatics)

Hence India is in a league of introducing new kind of programs and subject in the line of western countries. Development of Indian education sector is very much valuable for general development. Universities etc are doing well in recent past though there are many challenges and issues etc key factors in this regard.

Findings

As far as this study is concerned. It is noted that India is going well in terms of offering new age, skill-based, and emerging programs in the field of Engineering. The following are most important concern in this regard—

- In Engineering and Technological sector, most popular degrees are BTech and BE and most common subjects are Computer Science, Information Technology. Though a few universities Information and Communication Technology program also started.
- Few universities started in offering CSE, IT and latest Information and Communication Technology programs at BTech level. It is worthy to note that in India BTech and BE both are considered as equivalent.
- Among the 279 universities, 180 universities started BTech in the most commonly available subject called CSE. While among them 63 universities offering both IT as well as CS/CSE Degrees.
- Skill-based specializations are the key to development and employment generation. It is noted that 40 universities have started emerging subjects in the areas of Cloud Computing, Cyber Security, Networking, Big Data etc.
- Domain-based Informatics first time popularized in academics and started few of them are Health Informatics, Tele Informatics. Though Geo Informatics as specialization is also new in many contexts.

Suggestion

- Private Universities are self-financed in nature and the trend is rising. It is better to start the universities with skill-based programs only rather than general and traditional education for different reasons.

- For skill-based emerging programs universities may start tie up with other universities/industry due to betterment of mutual understanding and nurturing better interdisciplinary research.
- Joint degrees may be also provided in Collaboration and mutual understanding with the industries, organizations, and corporate houses to add value to the certificates globally.
- Financial assistance may be provided to the superior skill-based and needed programs offered by the private universities through different schemes of the Government for the betterment of the society, concerned sector, and obviously for employment generation.
- Gradually other areas of specializations may also be started in skill-based technological areas and also in domain-specific areas of study.
- Foreign collaboration with the industries and universities, research centres may be undertaken.

Conclusion

India is developing rapidly in education and economy. It is a home to a large number of higher education institutions and academic bodies around the world. India being world attraction, in terms of young manpower, has many numbers of engineering colleges and is offering many innovative degrees at bachelor and masters level. Though, there are many issues noticed in recent past as far as the educational situation and quality is concerned. Private Colleges and Universities need better control and authority from the Government perspective. India is rising towards a developed nation and its GDP is also growing hence in this stage universities are moving towards offering collaborative programs, emerging areas of study. It is worthy to mention that collaboration and mutual understanding with the industries, organizations, and corporate houses are always giving better results for the right solution and fulfillment of the objectives of these private universities in terms of providing innovative and value-based courses. Proper funding and infrastructure need to bring among the programs and universities. It is important to note that among 289 universities 180 universities offer BTech programs in various engineering subjects and a good percentage of institutions are offering general BTech/BE in CSE/IT and also expected to start new age specializations with or at-least liaison with the industries and corporate houses [7], [10]. Last but not the least, universities which have started emerging super specialty programs as a specialization may enter into the full-fledged degrees in near future if scope and demand available based on the market conditions.

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